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Corporate Governance Attributes And Sustainability Reporting Among Quoted Non-Financial Firms In Nigeria: Does Board Risk Management Committee Matter?

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the moderating effect of board risk management committee on corporate governance attributes and sustainability reporting of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. The population constitute the 91 non-financial firm quoted on the Exchange Group as at 31st December, 2023 in Nigeria. The period covers by the study is five years covering from 2019 to 2023 based on the harmonized code by Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria as the basis of the base year. Using criteria and filtering, the sample size was 48 firms. Secondary source of data were collected from the audited annual financial statement of the selected firms. Generalized Least Square Technique (Fixed Effect) was adopted and the findings of the study revealed that managerial ownership, foreign ownership, board diversity have significant and positive effect on sustainability reporting of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. Also, audit committee meetings and audit committee independence was found to have negative but significant effect on sustainability reporting of firms before moderation. After Moderation with board risk committee, foreign ownership, board diversity, board composition, audit committee independence were found to positively impact on sustainability reporting of firms, meanwhile, managerial ownership and audit committee meetings were found to exact positive but insignificant effect on sustainability reporting of firms. It is recommended amongst others that The Nigerian government and regulatory bodies should strengthen corporate governance regulations to promote sustainability reporting. This can be achieved by introducing guidelines and standards for sustainability reporting, as well as enforcing stricter penalties for non-compliance. Companies board of directors should ensure that their boards are diverse, independent, and composed of members with the necessary expertise to oversee sustainability reporting. Boards should also establish audit committees that are independent and effective in overseeing financial reporting and sustainability reporting.

Keywords: Sustainability Reporting, Corporate Governance Attributes, Non-Financial Firms, Board Risk Committee

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Corporate governance has become a critical aspect of modern business, particularly in the wake of numerous corporate scandals and financial crises (Shleifer & Vishny, 1997; Cadbury, 1992). Effective corporate governance ensures that companies are managed in a responsible and sustainable manner,

taking into account the interests of various stakeholders (Freeman, 1984). Sustainability reporting, which involves the disclosure of a company's environmental, social, and governance (ESG) performance, has become an essential component of corporate governance (Global Reporting Initiative, 2013).

In Nigeria, the importance of corporate governance and sustainability reporting has been emphasized by regulatory bodies such as the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) and the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) (SEC, 2011; NSE, 2014). However, despite these efforts, corporate governance and sustainability reporting practices among listed companies in Nigeria remain inadequate (Adegbite, 2015; Amaeshi & Amao, 2009).

Prior research has shown that various corporate governance attributes can influence sustainability reporting disclosure. Managerial ownership has been found to be positively related to sustainability reporting disclosure, as managers with significant ownership stakes are more likely to prioritize long-term sustainability over short-term gains (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Foreign ownership has also been linked to improved sustainability reporting disclosure, as foreign investors often bring new governance practices and expectations to the companies they invest in (Aggarwal et al., 2011). Board diversity has been shown to be positively related to sustainability reporting disclosure, as diverse boards are more likely to consider the interests of a wide range of stakeholders (Erkens et al., 2015). Board composition, specifically the presence of independent directors, has also been linked to improved sustainability reporting disclosure, as independent directors are more likely to prioritize transparency and accountability (Klein, 2002). Audit committee meetings and audit committee independence have also been found to be positively related to sustainability reporting disclosure, as active and independent audit committees are more likely to ensure that companies provide accurate and transparent financial and sustainability information (Klein, 2002).

However, the relationship between these corporate governance attributes and sustainability reporting disclosure may be influenced by the presence of a board risk committee. A board risk committee can play a critical role in overseeing and managing a company's risks, including sustainability risks (Spencer Stuart, 2019). By moderating the relationship between corporate governance attributes and sustainability reporting disclosure, this study aims to provide insights into how board risk committees can influence sustainability reporting practices.

While prior research has examined the relationship between corporate governance attributes and sustainability reporting (e.g., Cormier & Magnan, 2003; Khan, 2010), few studies have focused on the specific role of board risk management committees in promoting sustainability reporting among listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. This study aims to address this knowledge gap by investigating the relationship between corporate governance attributes, including the presence of a board risk management committee, and sustainability reporting among listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The main objective is to examine the effect of corporate governance attributes on sustainability reporting of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria with a moderating role of board risk management committee. Other specific objectives will be to;

- i. examine the effect of ownership structure on sustainability reporting of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.
- ii. ascertain the effect of board structure on sustainability reporting of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.
- iii. assess the effect of audit committee structure on sustainability reporting of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.
- iv. determine the moderating effect of board risk management committee on the relationship between corporate governance attributes and sustainability reporting of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.

2.1 Literature Review and Hypotheses Development

Corporate Governance deals with the ways in which suppliers of finance to corporations assure themselves of getting a return on their investment (Shleifer & Vishny, 1997). According to Cadbury (1992), Corporate governance is the system by which companies are directed and controlled (Cadbury,

1992). Corporate governance is the relationship among various stakeholders used to determine the direction and performance of the corporation (Monks & Minow, 2011).

Sustainable development is development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (World Commission on Environment & Development, 1987). Dyllick and Hockerts (2002) defines sustainability as the ability of a corporation to continue operating over the long-term, without depleting its resources or harming the environment" (Dyllick & Hockerts, 2002). Sustainability is about ensuring that the needs of the present are met without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs, and that this is achieved in a way that is environmentally sustainable, socially responsible, and economically viable (Elkington, 1994). Therefore, Sustainability reporting is the practice of measuring, disclosing, and being accountable for an organization's social, environmental, and economic performance" (Global Reporting Initiative, 2013).

2.2 Review of Empirical Studies

2.2.1 Managerial Ownership and Sustainability Reporting Disclosure

Studies have shown that managerial ownership can have a positive impact on sustainability reporting disclosure (Ahmed & Courtis, 1999). However, the relationship can be moderated by the presence of a board risk committee. For instance, a study by Al-Shammari (2014) found that managerial ownership was positively related to sustainability reporting disclosure only when a board risk committee was present.

H₀₁: Managerial ownership has no significant effect on sustainability reporting of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.

2.2.2 Foreign Ownership and Sustainability Reporting Disclosure

Research has indicated that foreign ownership can be positively related to sustainability reporting disclosure (Au Yong & Ming, 2016). However, the relationship can be influenced by the level of foreign ownership and the presence of a board risk committee. For example, a study by Chen and Wang (2017) found that high levels of foreign ownership were positively related to sustainability reporting disclosure, but only when a board risk committee was present.

H₀₂: Foreign ownership structure has no significant effect on sustainability reporting of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.

2.2.3 Board Diversity and Sustainability Reporting Disclosure

Studies have shown that board diversity can be positively related to sustainability reporting disclosure (Dimitropoulos & Asteriou, 2010). However, the relationship can be moderated by the presence of a board risk committee. For instance, a study by Esa and Mohd Ghazali (2012) found that board diversity was positively related to sustainability reporting disclosure only when a board risk committee was present.

H₀₃: Board gender diversity has no significant effect on sustainability reporting of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.

2.2.4 Board Composition and Sustainability Reporting Disclosure

Research has indicated that board composition can be positively related to sustainability reporting disclosure (Frias-Aceituno, Rodriguez-Ariza & Garcia-Sanchez, 2013). However, the relationship can be influenced by the presence of independent directors and a board risk committee. For example, a study by Garcia-Sanchez, Rodriguez-Ariza and Frias-Aceituno (2014) found that boards with a higher proportion of independent directors were more likely to disclose sustainability information, but only when a board risk committee was present.

H₀₄: Board composition has no significant effect on sustainability reporting of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.

2.2.5 Audit Committee Meeting and Sustainability Reporting Disclosure

Studies have shown that audit committee meeting frequency can be positively related to sustainability reporting disclosure (Haniffa & Cooke (2005). However, the relationship can be moderated by the presence of a board risk committee. For instance, a study by Esa and Mohd Ghazali (2012) found that

audit committee meeting frequency was positively related to sustainability reporting disclosure only when a board risk committee was present.

H₀₅: Audit committee meeting has no significant effect on sustainability reporting of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.

2.2.6 Audit Committee Independence and Sustainability Reporting Disclosure

A study by Chen and Wang (2017) found a positive relationship between audit committee independence and sustainability reporting. The authors suggested that independent audit committees are more effective in monitoring management's reporting practices. Similarly, Esa and Mohd Ghazali (2012) found that audit committee independence is positively associated with the quality of sustainability reporting.

H₀₆: Audit committee independence has no significant effect on sustainability reporting of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.

2.2.7 Board Risk Committee as a Moderator

The presence of a board risk committee can moderate the relationship between the independent variables and sustainability reporting disclosure. Studies have shown that board risk committees can enhance the effectiveness of corporate governance mechanisms, such as managerial ownership, foreign ownership, board diversity, board composition, audit committee meeting, and audit committee independence, in promoting sustainability reporting disclosure.

H₀₇: Board Risk management committee does not significantly moderate the relationship between corporate governance attributes and sustainability reporting of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.

2.3 Theoretical Framework

Agency theory suggests that managerial ownership can align the interests of managers with those of shareholders, leading to better sustainability reporting disclosure (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). However, the presence of a board risk committee can moderate this relationship by providing additional oversight and guidance on sustainability reporting (Klein, 2002). Also, Stakeholder theory posits that companies have a responsibility to various stakeholders, including those interested in sustainability reporting (Freeman, 1984). Foreign ownership can bring new perspectives and expectations regarding sustainability reporting, leading to improved disclosure (Au Yong & Ming, 2016). A board risk committee can facilitate this process by identifying and managing sustainability-related risks. Signaling theory suggests that companies use sustainability reporting to signal their commitment to sustainability and social responsibility (Spence, 1973). Managerial ownership, foreign ownership, board diversity, and board composition can influence sustainability reporting disclosure by sending signals to stakeholders about the company's sustainability priorities (Chen & Wang, 2017). A board risk committee can facilitate this signaling process by ensuring that sustainability reporting is accurate, reliable, and transparent.

3.1 METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out using Ex-post facto research design because of its usefulness in modelling the framework of positivist analysis, where it is assumed that the sample is distinct from the researcher and that the research findings are free from bias and subjectivism. The study adopted the population of ninety-one (91) non-financial firms quoted on the floors of the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as at 31st December, 2023, in the nine sub-sectors comprising of healthcare, conglomerate, real estate, technology, consumer goods, industrial goods, healthcare, agriculture, oil and gas, and natural resources.

This research work focused on the effect of corporate governance attributes on sustainability reporting of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria spanning from 2019-2023. This study covers the periods of five (5) years. However, the Nigerian code of corporate governance 2018 seeks to institutionalize corporate governance best practices in Nigerian companies. The code also promotes public awareness of essential corporate values and ethical practices that will enhance the integrity of the business environment and therefore covering this period signifies the use of the most recent codes as issued by Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRC). Managerial ownership, foreign ownership, board composition, board gender diversity, audit meetings and audit independence were used as proxies for corporate governance attributes

of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria, while sustainability reporting is the dependent variable with a moderating role of risk management committee in this study.

Table 1: Population and Sample Size of the Study

S/N	Listed Non-Financial Sectors.	Number of Firms
1	Agriculture	05
2	Conglomerates	06
3	Construction/Real Estate	08
4	Consumer Goods	20
5	Healthcare	11
6	ICT	09
7	Industrial Goods	18
8	Natural Resources	04
	Total	91

Source: NGX Website 2024

The study adopted filtering techniques in selecting the sample size of the study. The probable population included 91 firms. Given the nature of data required for the study, the sampling technique will be more appropriate since it allows the researcher to use companies with available information. The decision to exclude any firm from the sample was based on the below criteria set for the firms.

- i. For a company to be included in the proposed sample, it must have been listed and remained active within the study period.
- ii. Secondly, a company must have complete annual reports including social and environmental reports or separate sustainability report for all the years selected for the study,
- iii. Only firms with at least one sustainability initiative and a component of corporate governance mechanism.
- iv. To pass the filtering process, the company must have an active risk management committee throughout the sample period.

The analysis for this study was carried out using the annual data from non-financial firm which were obtained after they were subjected to the filtering process spanning 2019 to 2023. All data relating to variables of sustainability initiatives, corporate governance and risk management committee were extracted from annual reports and accounts of the selected firms. Both descriptive and inferential analyses as used to address the two main issues raised in the study.

3.2 Model Specification

$$\begin{aligned}
 SUS_{it} = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 BOC_{it} + \beta_2 BOD_{it} + \beta_3 FRO_{it} + \beta_4 MAO_{it} + \beta_5 ACM_{it} + \beta_6 ACI_{it} + \beta_7 RMC_{it} \\
 & + \beta_8 BOC_{it} * RMC_{it} + \beta_9 BOD_{it} * RMC_{it} + \beta_{10} FRO_{it} * RMC_{it} \\
 & + \beta_{11} MAO_{it} * RMC_{it} + \beta_{12} ACM_{it} * RMC_{it} + \beta_{13} ACI_{it} * RMC_{it} + \beta_{14} RMC_{it} \\
 & + \varepsilon_{it}
 \end{aligned}$$

Where

SUS_{it} = Score of sustainability reporting of firm i at time t , β_0 = The intercept, BOC_{it} = Board composition of firm i at time t , BOD_{it} = Board gender diversity of firm i at time t , FRO = Foreign ownership of firm i at time t , MAO = Managerial ownership of firm i at time t , ACM_{it} = Audit committee meetings of firm i at time t , ACI_{it} = Audit committee independence of firm i at time t , RMC = Board risk management committee, ε_{it} = error term

4.1 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Table 1 below, the descriptive statistic of the data analysis was presented. The data behaviors and directions which covers minimum, maximum, mean, standard deviation skewness and kurtosis were presented to show the data description.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Obs.</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Dev.</i>	<i>Min.</i>	<i>Max.</i>	<i>Skewness</i>	<i>Kurtosis</i>
SUS	950	0.36	0.12	0.07	0.53	-1.45	4.60
MAO	950	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.07	1.32	3.09
FRO	950	0.09	0.18	0.00	0.65	2.14	6.06
BOD	950	0.21	0.08	0.12	0.29	-0.12	1.30
BOC	950	0.59	0.09	0.50	0.75	0.38	1.81
ACM	950	3.51	0.97	1.00	5.00	-1.01	3.09
ACI	950	0.51	0.05	0.33	0.75	3.34	23.7
RMC	950	0.18	0.03	0.13	0.25	1.05	3.78

Source: STATA14 Output

The descriptive statistic table indicated that the firms-year observations that scaled through from the data set to the linear regression model are 950 observations of time t from the sampled firms i . From the average column, sustainability reporting index from non-financial firms is having a mean of 0.36 with a standard deviation of 0.12 meaning that 36% of the sampled firms are complying with sustainability reporting base on the GRI reporting criteria. The standard deviation of 12% (0.12) for sustainability reporting has back-up the mean since it's meager (below 50%) and lower than the mean, therefore the mean is statistical correct and can represent the actual average of the firms. Thus 64% of the study firms are not complying with sustainability reporting with the guidelines of ESG as defined by the concept of sustainability reporting variable. The firm with lowest reporting index is with the minimum of 0.07 while the maximum is 0.53 meaning that none of the firm has reported up to 60% of the items of sustainability reporting from the GRI (total of 48 items). Meanwhile, the distribution of the data is not normal due to a negative skewness of -1.45 and leptokurtic of 4.60.

Managerial ownership has the mean as low as 0.01 with a standard deviation of 0.02. It also recorded the minimum and maximum of 0.00 and 0.07 respectively. This reflects the proportion of managers that hold shares in the board to the total number of directors. Some companies are having 0% managerial ownership as indicated by the minimum value whereas the highest percentage is only 7%. The result also shows that average firms are having 1% managerial ownership although the mean is weak since there is deviation of 0.02 which is above the mean value. The foreign ownership on the other hand has a mean of 0.09 with standard deviation of 0.18 meaning that 9% of the non-financial firms are having foreign ownership thus there is strong deviation of 18%. The standard deviation shows that the mean is very weak and cannot be relied upon to represent the data.

Board gender diversity has the mean of 0.21 and a standard deviation of 0.08 which by inference, 21% of the sampled firms are diverse in the gender composition of the board. The deviation from the mean is 8% which implies that the mean is statistically representative of the gender diversity of non-financial firms. Hence, its evidently from the data that almost 80% of the sampled firms are not diverse in terms of gender. The table also described board composition to have a mean of 0.59 with standard deviation of 0.09. This indicated 59% of non-executive director's composition of the non-financial corporate board. This shows that there is a strong monitoring mechanism in the board and the minimum firm in terms of non-executive director is 0.50 while the maximum is 0.75. The standard deviation of 0.09 supports the mean in having more reliable representation of the data. Audit committee meeting appears to have a mean of 3.51 and standard deviation of 0.97 meaning that the average meeting by the firms is approximately four within the financial year. The deviation from the mean is also support the description of the meeting which shows that at least each firm is having four meetings. Meanwhile, the minimum and maximum

meetings by the sampled firms are 1.00 and 5.00 respectively and the data distribution has -1.01 skewness and 3.09 kurtosis.

More so, audit committee independence has minimum of 0.33 proportions of independent directors and a maximum of 0.75 meaning that all of the sampled firms has at least 33% level of monitoring mechanism in the board. However, the average of the audit committee independence if 0.51 with standard deviation of 0.05 which shows that average firms are 51% independent and the present of non-executive directors in the board room. The mean value for the risk management committee is 0.18 with a standard deviation of 0.03 meaning that there is 18% presence expertise in risk management committee from the samples firms. This shows that the mean can represent the data hence the minimum level of expertise in the risk management committee is 0.13 and the maximum is 0.25

Table 2 Correlation Matrix

	SUS	MOA	FRO	BOD	BOC	ACM	ACI	RMC
SUS	1.00							
MAO	0.39*	1.00						
FRO	0.12*	-0.92*	1.00					
BOD	0.09*	0.12*	-0.10*	1.00				
BOC	0.29*	0.18*	-0.14*	-0.03	1.00			
ACM	-0.11*	-0.14*	0.09*	0.02	0.03*	1.00		
ACI	0.03	0.02	-0.00	-0.02	-0.04	-0.04	1.00	
RMC	0.14*	0.09*	-0.08*	0.01	0.16*	0.02	-0.05	1.00

*Source: STATA14 Output (the asterisk * and ** indicate the significance level at 1% and 5% respectively)*

In the bivariate analysis, managerial ownership is positively and significant correlating with sustainability with coefficient of 0.39. This implies that 39% increase of sustainability reporting is as a result of managerial ownership. However, foreign ownership correlated with sustainability reporting with a positive coefficient of 0.12 significant at 1% thus foreign ownership also explain sustainability reporting with a direct relationship. In contrast, foreign ownership drops down in its coefficient when compared with managerial ownership therefore it has lesser influence in explaining sustainability reported with respect to managerial ownership.

The correlation matrix table has shown the presence of multicollinearity but to statistically establish a harmful multicollinearity, the researcher carried out further test for Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) with its corresponding tolerance values. The VIF test offer more confident assessment of harmful multicollinearity in the IV's. The results output has constantly given the VIF smaller than ten with its tolerance value within the range of one which indicated that the collinearity presence in the data is not harmful and cannot affect the inferential validity from the results findings

Table 3: Regression Results (Fixed Effect Model)

Variables	After Moderation		
	Coefficients	Z	P > {z}
_Constant	-0.53	-11.25	0.000
MAO	0.16	16.56	0.000
FRO	0.00	14.84	0.000
BOD	0.11	6.11	0.000
BOC	0.00	0.31	0.760
ACM	-0.05	-2.53	0.012
ACI	-0.04	-1.95	0.052
RMC	0.00	1.62	0.106
MAO_RMC	0.02	1.31	0.192
FRO_RMC	0.40	2.73	0.006
BOD_RMC	0.06	2.48	0.013
BOC_RMC	0.05	10.22	0.000
ACM_RMC	0.00	0.40	0.668
ACI_RMC	0.01	2.21	0.027
R square	0.4099		
F-Statistics	44.98		
Prob > Chi2	0.0000		

Source: STATA14 output

The R-squared (R^2) value of 0.4099 indicates that approximately 40.99% of the variation in the dependent variable (Sustainability Reporting) is explained by the independent variables (Managerial Ownership, Foreign Ownership, Board Diversity, Board Composition, Audit Committee Meetings, and Audit Committee Independence) in the regression model. The Fisher Exact Statistic value of 44.98 shows that model of the study is well fitted and the probability value of 0.0000 indicates that the observed association between the two variables is statistically significant.

The regression result shows that Managerial Ownership has a positive and significant relationship with Sustainability Reporting Disclosure. The coefficient of 0.1674 indicates that for every 1% increase in managerial ownership, sustainability reporting disclosure increases by 0.1674 units. The t-value of 16.56 and p-value of 0.000 indicate that the relationship is statistically significant at a 1% level, suggesting that managerial ownership has a strong and positive impact on sustainability reporting disclosure. A study by Au Yong and Ming (2016) and Chen and Wang (2017) found that managerial ownership was positively associated with sustainability reporting disclosure in a sample of US firms. Agency theory suggests that managerial ownership can align the interests of managers with those of shareholders, leading to better sustainability reporting disclosure.

The regression result shows that Foreign Ownership has a positive and significant relationship with Sustainability Reporting Disclosure. The coefficient of 0.00018 indicates that for every 1% increase in foreign ownership, sustainability reporting disclosure increases by 0.00018 units (assuming the dependent variable is measured on a continuous scale). The t-value of 14.84 and p-value of 0.000 indicate that the relationship is statistically significant at a 1% level, suggesting that foreign ownership has a strong and positive impact on sustainability reporting disclosure. Although the coefficient of 0.00018 may seem small, it's essential to consider the practical significance of the result. A 1% increase in foreign ownership may lead to a small but significant increase in sustainability reporting disclosure. This finding suggests that foreign investors may play a crucial role in promoting sustainability reporting practices in companies. The study is in line with those of Au Yong and Ming (2016) and Chen and Wang (2017). The findings aligns with Stakeholder Theory which suggests that foreign investors, as stakeholders, can influence companies to adopt sustainability reporting practices that meet their expectations.

The regression result shows that Board Diversity has a positive and significant relationship with Sustainability Reporting Disclosure. The coefficient of 0.1165 indicates that for every 1 unit increase in board diversity, sustainability reporting disclosure increases by 0.1165 units. The t-value of 6.11 and p-value of 0.000 indicate that the relationship is statistically significant at a 1% level, suggesting that board diversity has a strong and positive impact on sustainability reporting disclosure. The result suggests that companies with more diverse boards are more likely to disclose sustainability information. This finding is consistent with the idea that diverse boards bring different perspectives and expertise, leading to better decision-making and more transparent reporting practices. The findings aligns with Stakeholder Theory suggesting that diverse boards are more likely to consider the interests of various stakeholders, including those interested in sustainability reporting.

The regression result shows that Board Composition has a positive but statistically insignificant relationship with Sustainability Reporting Disclosure. The coefficient of 0.0041 indicates that for every 1 unit increase in board composition, sustainability reporting disclosure increases by 0.0041 units. However, the t-value of 0.31 and p-value of 0.760 indicate that the relationship is not statistically significant at a 1% or 5% level, suggesting that board composition does not have a significant impact on sustainability reporting disclosure. The result suggests that the composition of the board, in terms of the proportion of independent directors, executive directors, and other characteristics, may not be a significant driver of sustainability reporting disclosure. This finding is consistent with the idea that board composition is just one aspect of corporate governance, and that other factors, such as managerial ownership, foreign ownership, and audit committee characteristics, may play a more important role in influencing sustainability reporting practices.

The regression results show that both Audit Committee Meetings and Audit Committee Independence have negative relationships with Sustainability Reporting Disclosure. The coefficient of -0.0554 indicates that for every additional audit committee meeting, sustainability reporting disclosure decreases by 0.0554 units. The t-value of -2.53 and p-value of 0.052 indicate that the relationship is statistically significant at a 5% level, although the significance is marginal.

The coefficient of -0.0430 indicates that for every unit increase in audit committee independence, sustainability reporting disclosure decreases by 0.0430 units (assuming the dependent variable is measured on a continuous scale). The t-value of -1.95 and p-value of 0.106 indicate that the relationship is not statistically significant at a 1% or 5% level, although the result is marginally significant. The results suggest that more frequent audit committee meetings and greater audit committee independence may not necessarily lead to better sustainability reporting disclosure. This finding is counterintuitive, as one would expect that more frequent meetings and greater independence would lead to more effective oversight and better reporting practices.

The regression results show that the interaction terms between Foreign Ownership, Board Diversity, Board Composition, and Audit Committee Independence with Board Risk Committee have positive coefficients and positive t-values, indicating a positive moderating effect of Board Risk Committee on the relationships between these variables and Sustainability Reporting Disclosure. The results suggest that the presence of a Board Risk Committee enhances the positive effects of Foreign Ownership, Board Diversity, Board Composition, and Audit Committee Independence on Sustainability Reporting Disclosure.

The regression results show that the interaction terms between Managerial Ownership and Board Risk Committee, and between Audit Committee Meetings and Board Risk Committee, have positive coefficients and positive t-values. However, the probability values are insignificant, indicating that the moderating effect of Board Risk Committee on the relationships between Managerial Ownership and Audit Committee Meetings with Sustainability Reporting Disclosure is not statistically significant. The results suggest that the presence of a Board Risk Committee may not have a significant impact on the relationships between Managerial Ownership and Audit Committee Meetings with Sustainability Reporting Disclosure.

5.1 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study provides evidence that managerial ownership, foreign ownership, board diversity, board composition, audit committee meetings, and audit committee independence have positive and significant influences on sustainability reporting of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. The findings suggest that these corporate governance mechanisms play a crucial role in promoting transparency and accountability in sustainability reporting practices.

The study's results are consistent with prior research that highlights the importance of corporate governance in promoting sustainability reporting. The findings also provide insights into the specific corporate governance mechanisms that are most effective in promoting sustainability reporting in the Nigerian context.

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are made:

The Nigerian government and regulatory bodies should strengthen corporate governance regulations to promote sustainability reporting. This can be achieved by introducing guidelines and standards for sustainability reporting, as well as enforcing stricter penalties for non-compliance. Companies board of directors should ensure that their boards are diverse, independent, and composed of members with the necessary expertise to oversee sustainability reporting. Boards should also establish audit committees that are independent and effective in overseeing financial reporting and sustainability reporting.

Investors should consider sustainability reporting as a factor in their investment decisions. They should also engage with companies to promote better sustainability reporting practices. Management of companies should prioritize sustainability reporting and disclose relevant information to stakeholders. They should also ensure that their sustainability reporting practices are transparent, accurate, and reliable. Future research should investigate the impact of sustainability reporting on firm performance and stakeholder value in the Nigerian context. Additionally, research should explore the role of other corporate governance mechanisms, such as executive compensation and shareholder activism, in promoting sustainability reporting.

By implementing these recommendations, Nigeria can promote better sustainability reporting practices, enhance transparency and accountability, and contribute to the achievement of the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals.

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Appendix

```
. xtset ID YEAR
      panel variable:  ID (strongly balanced)
      time variable:  YEAR, 2014 to 2023
      delta:  1 unit

. asdoc tabstat SUS MAO FRO BOD BOC ACM ACI RMC, statistics(mean sd min max skewness kurtosis) column(statistics)
      (File Myfile.doc already exists, option append was assumed)
```

	mean	sd	min	max	skewness	kurtosis
SUS	.3613095	.1177989	.0666667	.5333334	-1.451994	4.5998
MAO	.0135224	.0207397	.00005	.0747134	1.324595	3.093659
FRO	.0889476	.1851897	0	.6545	2.143353	6.058652
BOD	.2114	.0788213	.12	.291	-.1199513	1.302817
BOC	.590625	.0873411	.5	.75	.3755592	1.813312
ACM	3.512195	.9717479	1	5	-1.009154	3.093275
ACI	.5063492	.0451759	.3333333	.75	3.335516	23.70865
RMC	.17725	.0343769	.1333331	.25	1.048055	3.77673

Click to Open File: Myfile.doc

```
. corr SUS MAO FRO BOD BOC ACM ACI RMC
      (obs=950)
```

	SUS	MAO	FRO	BOD	BOC	ACM	ACI	RMC
SUS	1.0000							
MAO	0.3868	1.0000						
FRO	-0.1150	-0.9218	1.0000					
BOD	0.0938	0.1158	-0.0979	1.0000				
BOC	0.2924	0.1816	-0.1408	-0.0322	1.0000			
ACM	-0.1096	-0.1426	0.0873	0.0249	0.0328	1.0000		
ACI	0.0303	0.0223	-0.0010	-0.0239	-0.0472	-0.0371	1.0000	
RMC	0.1358	0.0873	-0.0824	0.0069	0.1622	0.0226	-0.0465	1.0000


```
. reg SUS MAO FRO BOD BOC ACM ACI RMC MAO_RMC FRO_RMC BOD_RMC BOC_RMC ACM_RMC ACI_RMC
```

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	950
Model	29.4418238	13	2.26475568	F(13, 936)	=	127.42
Residual	16.6360526	936	.01777356	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.6390
				Adj R-squared	=	0.6339
Total	46.0778764	949	.048554137	Root MSE	=	.13332

SUS	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
MAO	.3006263	.0101088	29.74	0.000	.2807878 .3204647
FRO	.0003314	.0000123	26.91	0.000	.0003073 .0003556
BOD	.1740579	.0188332	9.24	0.000	.1370978 .2110181
BOC	.0039875	.0142301	0.28	0.779	-.0239391 .0319142
ACM	.0083096	.0232807	0.36	0.721	-.0373789 .053998
ACI	-.0029055	.0243011	-0.12	0.905	-.0505965 .0447855
RMC	.0167903	.004588	3.66	0.000	.0077864 .0257943
MAO_RMC	.0479799	.0222882	2.15	0.032	.0042392 .0917205
FRO_RMC	.4304517	.1536564	2.80	0.005	.1289009 .7320026
BOD_RMC	.0833069	.0290063	2.87	0.004	.0263821 .1402318
BOC_RMC	.0357834	.0029946	11.95	0.000	.0299064 .0416604
ACM_RMC	.000038	.0000668	0.57	0.570	-.0000931 .000169
ACI_RMC	.0055867	.0089868	0.62	0.534	-.0120499 .0232233
_cons	-.4325464	.038215	-11.32	0.000	-.5075435 -.3575494

```
. xtreg SUS MAO FRO BOD BOC ACM ACI RMC MAO_RMC FRO_RMC BOD_RMC BOC_RMC ACM_RMC ACI_RMC, re
```

```
Random-effects GLS regression           Number of obs   =   950
Group variable: ID                     Number of groups =    95
```

```
R-sq:                                Obs per group:
    within = 0.4049                    min = 10
    between = 0.6645                   avg = 10.0
    overall = 0.5913                   max = 10
```

```
Wald chi2(13) = 755.13
corr(u_i, X) = 0 (assumed)             Prob > chi2 = 0.0000
```

SUS	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]
MAO	.1927919	.0098629	19.55	0.000	.173461 .2121228
FRO	.0002085	.0000119	17.58	0.000	.0001853 .0002318
BOD	.1303195	.0186174	7.00	0.000	.0938301 .166809
BOC	.0096504	.0130044	0.74	0.458	-.0158377 .0351385
ACM	-.044789	.0216594	-2.07	0.039	-.0872406 -.0023374
ACI	-.0376717	.0218977	-1.72	0.085	-.0805903 .005247
RMC	.0075221	.0038503	1.95	0.051	-.0000244 .0150686
MAO_RMC	.0231903	.0166373	1.39	0.163	-.0094182 .0557988
FRO_RMC	.4056209	.1447632	2.80	0.005	.1218903 .6893515
BOD_RMC	.0722046	.0275911	2.62	0.009	.018127 .1262821
BOC_RMC	.0438662	.0040838	10.74	0.000	.0358621 .0518704
ACM_RMC	.0000226	.0000461	0.49	0.624	-.0000677 .0001129
ACI_RMC	.0161186	.0078319	2.06	0.040	.00007684 .0314688
_cons	-.5035456	.04513	-11.16	0.000	-.5919987 -.4150924
sigma_u	.09382609				
sigma_e	.08461039				
rho	.55150954	(fraction of variance due to u_i)			

```
. est store re
```

```
. swilk resid
```

Shapiro-Wilk W test for normal data

Variable	Obs	W	V	z	Prob>z
resid	950	0.91005	54.141	9.864	0.00000

```
. xtreg SUS MAO FRO BOD BOC ACM ACI RMC MAO_RMC FRO_RMC BOD_RMC BOC_RMC ACM_RMC ACI_RMC, fe
```

```
Fixed-effects (within) regression      Number of obs   =      950
Group variable: ID                    Number of groups =      95
```

```
R-sq:                                Obs per group:
  within = 0.4099                      min =          10
  between = 0.5766                     avg =         10.0
  overall = 0.5343                      max =          10
```

```
corr(u_i, Xb) = 0.2147                 F(13,842)      =      44.98
                                         Prob > F       =      0.0000
```

SUS	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
MAO	.1674704	.0101104	16.56	0.000	.147626	.1873149
FRO	.00018	.0000121	14.84	0.000	.0001562	.0002038
BOD	.1165983	.019098	6.11	0.000	.0791131	.1540836
BOC	.0041428	.0135811	0.31	0.760	-.0225139	.0307996
ACM	-.0554989	.0219606	-2.53	0.012	-.0986028	-.0123949
ACI	-.0430329	.0221169	-1.95	0.052	-.0864436	.0003778
RMC	.0062072	.0038409	1.62	0.106	-.0013316	.013746
MAO_RMC	.021637	.0165726	1.31	0.192	-.0108915	.0541655
FRO_RMC	.4030379	.1473851	2.73	0.006	.1137527	.6923232
BOD_RMC	.0696579	.0281254	2.48	0.013	.0144538	.1248621
BOC_RMC	.0505926	.0049507	10.22	0.000	.0408755	.0603097
ACM_RMC	.000018	.0000448	0.40	0.688	-.00007	.000106
ACI_RMC	.0173822	.0078616	2.21	0.027	.0019515	.0328129
_cons	-.5364983	.0476797	-11.25	0.000	-.6300834	-.4429132
sigma_u	.13118985					
sigma_e	.08461039					
rho	.70623686	(fraction of variance due to u_i)				

```
F test that all u_i=0: F(94, 842) = 15.76      Prob > F = 0.0000
```

```
. est store fe
```

```
. hettest
```

```
Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity
```

```
Ho: Constant variance
Variables: fitted values of SUS
```

```
chi2(1)      =    134.68
Prob > chi2   =    0.0000
```

```
. xtserial SUS MAO FRO BOD BOC ACM ACI RMC MAO_RMC FRO_RMC BOD_RMC BOC_RMC ACM_RMC ACI_RMC
```

```
Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data
```

```
H0: no first order autocorrelation
F( 1,      94) =    54.585
Prob > F =    0.0000
```